

REBIRTH OF A CITY: CASE OF MATERA SASSI ITALY

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INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to contribute to the paradigm of design education, practice, and research by establishing the importance of heritage conservation and the reuse of city infrastructure for sustainability, economic viability, and future growth.

Conservation of cities started as a concept in the early 1970s with the emergence of many abandoned towns globally. In his book *Conservation and Sustainability in Historic Cities*, Dennis Rodwell discussed the conservation of many historic European cities and how they are re-imagined into historic cultural precincts.

Similarly, in the Case of Matera, Sassi Italy was reborn from a complete abandonment of “Sassi” in the 1950s to a new dynamic cultural landscape, the European capital, in 2019. The paper will unfold the story of Matera from its origins as one of the oldest continuously inhabited towns in the world, its Architecture and cultural significance as the first human settlement in Italy dates back to the Paleolithic period to the current sustainable, resilient city in southern Italy. Matera has a unique cultural landscape that comprises natural habitat and manmade building typologies that sit perfectly with the morphology of its geographical topography.

The paper will explore heritage conservation and adaptive reuse strategies set for the Conservation of the Matera city landscape, the principles of infrastructure reuse, environmental sustainability, heritage protection, and the global economy. Furthermore, the paper will highlight parameters that listed Matera as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1993 and later designated as a European Cultural Capital in 2019.

Lastly, the paper unfolds design parameters and strategies that regain “Matera” presence on the world map by analyzing various project interventions, design charters, and adaptive reuse case studies, which created new building typologies, dynamic Interior environments and promote economic viability, new professions, future growth, resilience, and cultural identity for Matera Sassi Italy.

HERITAGE CONSERVATION

Heritage conservation was first coined in the 1960s after the increasing interest in protecting historic districts of European urban history. It was formalized in 1974 after the UNESCO Convention on World Heritage Sites and their conservation and protection. It was followed by several governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), including UNESCO, ICOMOS, ICOM, and ICCROM, followed by various international Charters. (Dennis Rodwell).

Heritage conservation aims to preserve a building's architectural character by preventing demolition and promoting restoration and reuse. This process seeks to protect the historical features of the built

environment, extending beyond just architecture to the conservation of cultural heritage. Burra's charter defines “heritage conservation as the practice of safeguarding and up-keeping a location to preserve its cultural importance.”

Heritage conservation of the city of Matera started in the 80s, after the town's abandonment during the 1960s; the first law applied in November 1986, law 771, states the “Conservation and recovery of Matera Sassi” in which the city center and the principal monuments were protected under law 771. In 1993, after Matera's inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage List, major laws were enforced to protect the historic character of the city in line with the Burra Charter, which states that the historical city center or the heritage perimeter remains unchanged over time and maintains its cultural intrinsic value while other parts are subject to significant changes.¹

In the case of Matera city, the heritage perimeters, buffer zones, and conservation practices are identified according to the UNESCO Heritage Urban Landscape approach (UNESCO, 2011) and its complex social and intrinsic values.

INTRODUCTION TO SASSI DI MATERA

Origin to 1993

Matera is one of the oldest cities in the world, dating back to the Paleolithic times.

It is located in the southern province of Bari, Italy, and it's known to be the only continuously inhabited city in the world and has traces of various Architecture periods. Matera has a unique cultural and urban context; natural caves, underground architecture, cisterns, farms, enclosures, churches, and palaces follow one another and coexist, excavated and built in the local stone ‘tufa.’²

Sassi of Matera or Stones of Matera refers to almost 3000 dwellings carved into the side of a vast canyon, and it's defined by UNESCO as “the most outstanding, intact example of a troglodyte settlement in the Mediterranean region, perfectly adapted to its terrain and ecosystem.”

Figure 1. Matera City and Landscape by UNESCO

The city's architectural landscape is a cluster of caves of various sizes, in which cisterns, reservoirs, and terraces are carved, which allows the collection and distribution of water for domestic and

agricultural use. The Cave structure is the co-existence of systems built and excavated into the rock; many caves are sloped downwards of various shapes and sizes, which maximizes the low winter sun angle and provides thermal comfort in summers and warm shelter in winters. The site is constructed as an outstanding example of bioclimatic traditional architecture, making it unique and significant worldwide.³

Figure 2. Adapted from P. Law and Architecture League

Sassi of Matera, as of today, is comprised of the ancient city of Matera, the park of rupestrian churches comprising churches, monasteries, hermitages, and other religious buildings. The entire region covers an area of 1016 hectares. It contains more than 1,500 dwellings, many shops, workshops, and stone churches.⁴

Sassi's historic center retains the distinction of two districts, **the Barisano and Caveoso**, the 17th-18th century backbone of the city called "**Piano.**" The top of the town is known as Civita, with its architectural monuments, and to the north and south are the houses, palaces, and courtyards of the Cavesano and Barisano districts.⁵

Figure 3. Adapted from SAASI | world heritage.

The city started to expand in the Greek times with significant importance of the city center known as Civita, and the defense walls in the town came in the Roman era with expanded living spaces. The most elaborate stonework dates back to the Renaissance when many caves were adorned with new facades and extended ceilings to make vaulted rooms. The Byzantine monks created the most splendid rock-hewn churches during the 12th and 13th centuries with exquisite frescoed interiors. The superposition of the construction reveals various stages in history; therefore, it was declared a Cultural heritage of humanity by UNESCO in 1993.⁶

The City of Matera saw an era of degradation, poverty, and decline in the 18th century and the 19th century; the modern city expands along the flat terrain of the ravine by developing administrative and religious buildings right where the ancient city uses its resources from like the storage of grains, water systems. The pits, barns, shared wells, and gardens on the flat plateau, the crucial centers of the Sassi infrastructure system, were buried and belonged to a new power structure.⁷

The major shift due to the laws and space allocation, resources led Matera to decay and made it a disgrace for Italy. The process reached its Peak in 1950 when a special law was passed to evacuate Sassi, and the relocation process started in the modern neighborhoods.⁸

In the 1950s, the site was considered essential for experimentation and innovation. Matera became the first city in southern Italy to be listed as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1993. The ‘Sassi’—alongside the Park of Rupestrian Churches, comprising more than one hundred religious buildings carved in the rocks—was inscribed in the UNESCO WHL. Among the various reasons and motivations for the inscription, specific Importance was acknowledged to the peculiar water collection system conceived and adopted by Ancient inhabitants consisting of rock reservoirs, caves, and dug ice houses that illustrate significant stages of development in human history, which is adapted perfectly to its geomorphological setting and ecosystem.⁹

Figure 4. Adapted from ECOC Matera 2019

UNESCO Parameters for the City of Matera

Following are the parameters due to which Matera was listed in the WHL and the UNESCO World Heritage Sites in 1993.

1. The Sassi and the Park of the Rupestrian Churches of Matera represent an outstanding rock-cut settlement, adapted perfectly to its geomorphological setting and ecosystem and exhibiting continuity over two millennia.
2. The town and park constitute an outstanding example of an architectural ensemble and landscape illustrating several significant stages in human history.
3. The town and park represent an outstanding example of a traditional human settlement and land use, showing the evolution of a culture that has maintained a harmonious relationship with its natural environment over time.

The **Park of Rupestrian Churches** is located in the territory of Matera and Montescaglioso. Listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site and measuring 8,000 hectares, the park contains more than 150 ancient cave churches, some hidden under dense vegetation on the banks of the ravine.

Figure 5. Park of rupestrian churches WHS

Timeline of events and strategies after 1993-2030

After the inclusion in the WHL, Matera saw an incredible rise in the number of tourists. It also attracted various research-based groups that aim to study the city's dynamic character and document the cityscape for future interventions and growth. The Commune di Matera (2014-2019) and various international agencies worked toward consolidating heritage perimeters, buffer zones, mapping projects, including digital heritage, focusing on tangible and intangible heritage, collecting traditions, etc. Along with the continuous efforts from the local community and officials in 2014, the city was titled the European Culture Capital for the year 2019, which marks one of the most critical events in the History of Matera Sassi—followed by various thematic events, activities, exhibitions, conferences, books, researchers, writers, and artists, especially those focused on underground heritage and its reuse. In 2019, the city of Sassi developed a new paradigm of urban planning and scholarly research based on the critical principles of infrastructure reuse, environmental sustainability, material economy for future growth, sustainability, and economic viability.¹⁰¹¹

Central heritage planning and design intervention strategies were materialized during this time, which focused on the concept of living heritage, re-inventing of new building functions, and sustainable initiatives for the landscape of Sassi, which were aimed to minimize the physical impact of interventions and focused on building sustainable and valuable infrastructure. The premise is to use scientific, creative, and technological expertise that combines Matera's exceptional landscape with new digital frameworks to create a new city identity.

Following the year 2019, as the cultural capital of Europe, the I-DEA Museum, the open design school, Arca di Prometeo Theatre, and collaborative research linkages were developed with the University of Bari, School of Advance Training in Restoration, University of Basilicata, and the University of Lecca which towards developing strategies, policies, projects, and interventions focused on the redevelopment of Sassi.¹²

HOMME Charter and CONAF 2023

In 2021, The HOMME charter was developed, which focuses on Mega events in heritage-rich cities in Europe and provides principles and recommendations that can help cities Reuse and adapt existing infrastructure and facilities or design context-sensitive interventions that can benefit from meaningful uses of places that have proved to be resilient over time. It has given a new layer to the existing development in the Matera city landscape, followed by the CONAF 2023-2030 Agenda for cities based on Food safety, livable towns, environmental safety, and sustainable forest management.¹³¹⁴

HERITAGE CONSERVATION STRATEGIES FOR MATERA

The main conservation approaches for the Matera Saasi are based on the collective work of different national and international organizations and charters.

1. The development of the cultural landscape is the leading conservation approach for the city with the newly emerging paradigms, the humanistic and the ecological paradigms. This approach aligns with (2011), a unifying approach to the landscape, a systematic vision that includes all the factors and interdependencies between natural and artificial components. (UNESCO, 2011)
2. City conservation is a multi-faceted approach that integrates Urban Landscape, nature, people, and intrinsic value, which aligns with the BURRA charter (1979-2013).
3. The use of material economy as a central force for the adaptive reuse of a city focuses on future growth, sustainability, and economic viability.¹⁵
4. Use of technology for mapping the complex landscape of Matera, with the help of IOT devices, optimization of digital surveys, and photo-geometric techniques for determining the potential use of heritage.¹⁶
5. Another vital strategy utilized in the Sassi is the flexibility and adaptability of the urban environment. – Spaces, buildings, and infrastructure; the construction chain characterized by efficient dismantling and separation, etc.

Adaptive reuse intervention strategies for Matera

Following are the strategies used in the landscape of Sassi Matera to minimize the physical impact of interventions according to the European agenda, the BURRA charter, ECOC, HUL, Charters of Matera, HOMME, UNESCO parameters, UBH and (Varriale R).

1. Four different levels of reuse have been recognized:

Re-inventing cultural heritage: interpretation of historical functions, restoration, fruition as an artistic site (e.g., installations of technological instruments to communicate underground culture, reconstruction of underground life, etc.).

2. **Re-introducing old functions:** The historical sites are restored and used again according to new parameters (e.g., productive spaces with the adoption of contemporary hygienic and security standards).

3. **Re-interpreting historical spaces:** The sites are restored, and new functions are allocated, but the communicative role is preserved (e.g., shops, hotels, restaurants, and urban facilities in pre-existent underground spaces).

4. **Re-building:** New caved artifacts are built with the adoption of the historical negative building culture (e.g., duplication of the original).

Case Studies on Re-inventing Cultural Heritage

Palombaro Cistern – Piano

Palombaro Lungo is a 16th-century Water Cathedral located under the central Piazza Vittorio Veneto in the piano district of Matera. It served as a water supply source and a reservoir where rainwater and spring water from the surrounding hills converged; it has 15m high tuff walls covered with a special waterproof plaster and a capacity of 5 million liters. The cistern symbolizes “Negative architecture, “created by subtracting material from the calcarenites.¹⁷

After being used for about a century and a half as a water reserve, with the construction of the Apulian Aqueduct in 1920, the Palombaro Lungo was unused and wholly abandoned. It was rediscovered in 1991, during the requalification works of Piazza Vittorio Veneto, and restored as a Museum of Water.¹⁸

Figure 6. Palombaro Water cathedral

Case Studies on Re-interpreting Cultural Heritage

Oi Mari restaurant – Civita

The 17th-century-old cave church has been reimagined as a restaurant in the heart of the Civita district. New spaces within the cave were created through subtraction, adding to the existing living areas by removing material from the calcarenites. All the rooms are treated in the same way. The site has been enhanced, exposing the limestone completely and introducing a few simple, functional furnishings.¹⁹

Figure 7. Ol Mari Restaurant Plan and Details

Aquatic Cave Hotel and Wellness Retreat - Caveoso

Aquatio is a wellness retreat hotel in the Sasso Caveoso district of Matera, dating back to the thirteenth century. This exclusive hotel is now a UNESCO World Heritage Site, has 35 luxury suites, a Mediterranean restaurant, a lobby bar and lounge area, a 500-m² spa with natural pools dating back to the 9th century, and a heated indoor swimming pool.²⁰

Simone Michelle designs them as a wellness retreat, combining old aesthetics and modern technology. The rooms in this hotel stand out for their size and minimalist decoration, where the natural stone has a dual function: Construction and Decoration. The space's lighting has been kept discrete to create emotions, as described by Simone Michelle.²¹

The hotel rooms are distinguished as excavated or built-up typology; the cave rooms are hidden in the structure complex with all modern age comforts and are spacious with minimal interiors and furnishing. The built suites comprised the upper part of the structure with ample natural light and breathtaking views of the ancient city dating back to the bronze ages.

Figure 8. The Aquatic Luxury Hotel adapted from Arch Daily

Casa Cava - Barisano

Case cava is a unique cultural center carved entirely from rock in the Sassi Barisano district. Originally a sizeable tuff quarry in the 17th century, it was later used as a dumping ground in the 19th century before being abandoned. However, it was transformed into the world's first underground cultural center and theatre, boasting around 900 square meters of an auditorium accommodating up to 140 people. This center is considered a hub for youth creativity and a significant step towards a cultural revival of Matera.²²

Figure 9. Casa Cava by Cultural Heritage Online

New research, author findings supported by research methods, and site visits suggest that rebuilding has never been practiced in Matera. Instead, the interventions focus on re-invention, re-interpretation, and innovation. The image below displays an analytical study conducted on four different interior typologies in Matera to analyze the type of Design intervention for the further development of research. It also features two projects that are part of world heritage sites: Aquatio Luxury Hotel and Spa and Casa Cava Cultural Center, which redefines creativity, innovation, and sustainable design solutions. The below image model is adapted from (Varriale R.) while the case study analysis and research findings are by the author.

Functional classification	Adaptive reuse strategies	Design Parameters	New typologies	Projects	
17 th century old cave church in the Civita district	Intervention Re-interpreting	Subtractive strategy	Restaurant	Oi Mari restaurant	
16 th -century Water cistern Underground water cathedral "al piano"	Installation re-Inventing	Protection of artifacts and architectural elements	Museum Water cathedral	Il Palombaro	
13 th -century cave complex Sasso Caveoso UNESCO perimeter Village cave complex	Intervention Re-interpreting	Old cisterns were connected Tuff caves The original complex is used for the hotel	Luxury Hotel and Spa 2018	Aquatio cave hotel	
Tuff quarry Sasso Barisano	Intervention Re-interpreting	Tuff quarry Removal of debris cleaning	Underground cultural Centre 2019 ECOC	Casa Cava Multipurpose complex	

Figure 10. Analysis of the Case Studies interior Intervention typology

CONCLUSION

Matera is a remarkable cultural landscape that holds immense cultural and intrinsic significance. It is known as the world's most resilient city that recently transformed a decaying, invisible town in southern Italy into one of Europe's most celebrated cities. Matera's revival story is exceptional, as it emerged from a deteriorating city in the 1930s and was declared a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1993, regaining its importance worldwide.

Matera's journey to becoming the Cultural capital of Europe in 2019 is a prime example of infrastructure reuse and environmental sustainability. Its streets, buildings, monuments, and heritage precincts embody the true spirit of resilience and growth, showcasing the ability to transform decaying spaces into new interior environments for future use.

The modern reuse of the Sassi historic interior is incredibly inventive, featuring caves, hotels, restaurants, cafes, galleries, cave clubs, mediation spas, swimming pool art galleries, Cultural centers, living museums, and the contemporary Art museum MUSMA. These innovative and futuristic interior typologies add a new layer of urbanism to the existing cultural landscape, designed to meet the demands of present and future generations while preserving the authenticity of the city fabric.

NOTES

¹ Vito D. Porcari, Antonella Guida, “Modernity and Tradition in the Sassi of Matera Italy”. Smart community and underground (hypogeum) city, *Journal of Architectural Conservation*, 28:2, (2022):126-143, DOI: 10.1080/13556207.2022.2085452.

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³ Cardinale, Tiziana and Pavia, Laura and Zucchi, Giovanni, “The city of Matera and the Sassi: smart places with a Dantean attraction.” REAL CORP 2014 – PLAN IT SMART! Clever Solutions for Smart Cities. (Proceedings of 19th International Conference on Urban Planning, Regional Development and Information Society. pp. 665-674, 2014).

⁴ The Sassi and the Park of the Rupestrian Churches of Matera,” UNESCO World Heritage Site, accessed June 10, 2023, <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/670/documents/>.

⁵ Antonietta Varasano, “An IoT Smart Infrastructure for S. Domenico Church in Matera’s “Sassi”: A Multiscale Perspective to Build Heritage Conservation”. Construction Technologies Institute–National Research Council of Italy, 70124 Bari, Italy *Sustainability* 12(16) (2020) 6553; doi.10.3390/su12166553.

⁶ “Matera the wonderful UNESCO World Heritage Site Sassi of Matera,” Cultural cities ITALIA.IT, accessed in May 10, 2023, <https://www.italia.it/en/basilicata/matera/guide-history-facts>.

⁷ Marcello Bernardo*, Francesco De Pascale. “Matera (Basilicata, Southern Italy): A European Model of Reuse, Sustainability and Resilience.” Department of Languages and Educational Sciences, University of Calabria, Italy. *Advances in Economics and Business* (1, 4) (2016):26-36, DOI: 10.13189/aeb.2016.040104.

⁸ Ippolita Mecca, “In situ experimentations for the compatibility and durability of the restorations, the case study of the Sassi of Matera.” Department of European and Mediterranean Cultures, University of Basilicata *Vitruvio International Journal of Architecture Technology and Sustainability Volume 1* (2016): 35 doi: 10.4995/vitruvio-ijats.2016.5686.

⁹ “The Sassi and Park of Rupestrian Churches in Matera,” UNESCO World Heritage Site ICOMOS 1992, accessed, February 24, 2023, <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/670/documents>

¹⁰ “European Cultural Capital, “Commune di Matera (2018b), accessed April 12, 2023, from <http://www.comune.matera.it/>.

¹¹ Antonietta Ivona, Antonella Rinella, Francesca Rinella, “Glocal tourism and resilient cities: Case of Matera “European Capital of culture 2019”, Department of Economy and Finance, University of Bari, History Society human studies Department, University of Salento, Lecce. *Sustainability* 11(15) (2019):4118, DOI:10.3390/su11154118.

¹² Michela Felicetti, “Cultural Innovation and Local Development: Matera as a Cultural district,” (Paper presentation in 2nd International Symposium “NEW METROPOLITAN PERSPECTIVES” - Strategic planning, spatial planning, economic programs, and decision support tools, through the implementation of Horizon/Europe2020. Isth2020, Reggio Calabria Italy 2016) 614 – 618.

¹³ Michela Felicetti, “Cultural Innovation and Local Development: Matera as a Cultural district,” (Paper presentation in 2nd International Symposium “NEW METROPOLITAN PERSPECTIVES” - Strategic planning, spatial planning, economic programs, and decision support tools, through the implementation of Horizon/Europe2020. Isth2020, Reggio Calabria Italy 2016) 614 – 618.

¹⁴ “European Cultural Capital, “Commune di Matera (2018b), accessed April 12, 2023, from <http://www.comune.matera.it/>.

¹⁵ Luigi Fusco, Francesca Nocca, Antonia Gravagnuolo. “Matera: city of nature, city of culture, city of regeneration. Towards a landscape-based and culture-based urban circular economy”, *Aestimum* 74 (2019): DOI: 10.13128/aestim-7007.

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¹⁷ Antonella Guida, Ippolita Mecca, “The PALOMBARO SASSI of Matera Italy, The interaction between Water and Construction Materials.” “(Paper presented at the 9th International Conference on NDT of Art, Jerusalem, Israel, and May 2018).

¹⁸ Antonella Guida, Ippolita Mecca, “The PALOMBARO SASSI of Matera Italy, The interaction between Water and Construction Materials.” “(Paper presented at the 9th International Conference on NDT of Art, Jerusalem, Israel, and May 2018).

¹⁹ “Oi Mari by Manca Studio.” Architectural record, Accessed June 04, 2023, <https://www.architecturalrecord.com/articles/13616-oi-mar%C3%AC-by-manca-studio>.

²⁰ “Aquatario Cave Luxury Hotel & SPA / Simone Micheli,” Arch daily, accessed May 23, 2023, <https://www.archdaily.com/920338/aquatario-cave-luxury-hotel-and-spa-simone-micheli>.

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